

A Data-Driven Lifetime Prediction Method for Thermally Aged SiC MOSFET Applications

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Co-funded by the European Union

Abstract

Power semiconductor switches, such as Metal-Oxide Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistor (MOSFETs), are widely utilized in solid-state power controllers (SSPC) of electric vehicles, aircrafts and trains. Predictive Health Monitoring (PHM), coupled with the reliability analysis of MOSFETs, are of utmost significance in power electronic systems. Among various PHM indicators, the ON-state resistance of MOSFETs stands out as a vital and indicative harbinger of failure. This paper introduces a data-driven methodology employing a Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) algorithm to predict the variations of the ON-state resistance. The experimental dataset was derived from subjecting the MOSFET to power cycling under thermal stress conditions. Furthermore, the model's efficacy was scrutinized utilizing a minor fraction of the dataset for training the LSTM algorithm, showcasing robust performance. Additionally, the proposed model was validated across diverse MOSFET degradation datasets, affirming its universal applicability.

I. Introduction

Prior studies have confirmed that fluctuations in the drain-to-source ON-state resistance ($R_{DS(ON)}$) of MOSFETs act as a principal marker of device failure, stemming from the degradation of wire bonds and the emergence of cracks in the die. Monitoring and forecasting the trajectory of $R_{DS(ON)}$ changes offers a direct assessment of the PHM and RUL of power MOSFETs [1,2].

Fig. 1. $\Delta R_{ds(on)}$ variations of various MOSFETs (IRF520NPbf).

Fig. 1 illustrates the exponential growth of data from MOSFETs, revealing the inadequacy of traditional methods for pattern detection. This paper introduces an LSTM framework to predict MOSFETs' Remaining Useful Life (RUL), leveraging extensive datasets for accurate, real-time prognostics in system PHM.

II. Flowchart of PHM Strategy

As shown in Fig.2, the general flowchart of designing PHM algorithm for a specific MOSFET normally contains 6 steps.

- ① Targeted MOSFET selection;
- ② Accelerated life-time testing and data obtaining;
- ③ Indicator identification;
- ④ Data preprocessing;
- ⑤ Life time Prediction based on LSTM algorithm;
- ⑥ Results analysis

Fig. 2. A general flowchart of PHM algorithm design for SiC-MOSFETs.

III. Results and Discussions

Fig. 3 displays prediction results. Using 20% training data yields a large error (RMSE of $8.3e^{-4}$, Fig.3(a)). Increasing training data progressively reduces errors: 25% (Fig.3(b)), 40% (RMSE of $3.9e^{-4}$, Fig.3(c)), and 60% training data significantly lowers RMSE to $3.5e^{-4}$ (Fig.3(d)). The simulation results demonstrate that the LSTM-based strategy effectively predicts the $R_{ds(on)}$ with increased training data. Future research will focus on designing data-driven online prediction methods.

Fig. 3. Predicting results with various training data. (a) Training Data/Testing Data: 20%, RMSE= $8.3e^{-4}$; (b) Training Data/Testing Data: 25%, RMSE= $6.6e^{-4}$; (c) Training Data/Testing Data: 40%, RMSE= $3.9e^{-4}$; (d) Training Data/Testing Data: 60%, RMSE= $3.5e^{-4}$.

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[2] M. J. Sathik, J. D. Navamani, A. Lavanya, Y. Yang, D. Almakhlis and F. Blaabjerg, "Reliability Analysis of Power Components in Restructured DC/DC Converters," in IEEE Transactions on Device and Materials Reliability, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 544-555, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TDMR.2021.3116941.